

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Laser induced graphene papers enabled functional composites for liquid monitoring

Yanan Wang

School of Mechanical Engineering & Automation, Beihang University

Address: No 37. Xueyuan Rd., Beijing, China 100191

E-mail: wyn158@buaa.edu.cn

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Outline

Background

Preparation of graphene paper

Results and discussions

Conclusions

Background

Composites corrosion presents a constant threat to the structural integrity of composites.

Laser induced graphene paper

The schematic diagram of roll-to-roll manufacturing, photographs of the largest LIGP, liquid sensor ; SEM、 TEM、 Raman and XRD characterization. (LIGP processed by 1.125 W).

Results and discussions

SEM images of LIGP processed at different power from 0.875w to 2.0 w, different structures including sheets structure, curled porous structure and fiber structure.

Results and discussions

LIGP-0.875 for detecting different amount of acetone with high reproducibility

Relative electrical resistance change of the micro-volume tests at different LIGP processed power

Results and discussions

LIGP sensor array for predicting the location of composites which threatened by harmful liquids

Conclusions

A flexible and portable LIGP-based liquid sensor with fast response and good reproducibility is reported. LIGP shows its advantages of lightweight, simple preparation, low cost, roll-to-roll production and environmental protection. Then, the possible sensing mechanism is proposed from the view-point of processing-structure-property relationship. Morphologies of LIGP determined barriers of charge carriers and their migration distance and resulted in different sensitivity. Based on the sensing results, LIGP sensor array is applicable to monitor the location of composites exposed to harmful liquids and predict the degree of erosion by organic solvents. The multifunctional LIGP liquid sensor with the scalable processing technique demonstrated in this work can be highly valuable in organic solvents transportation and smart composites preparation for developing self-monitoring solvents pipelines and smart anti-corrosion structures.

THANKS!!